

HOW TO IMPROVE SPEAKING COMPETENCE IN EFL CLASSROOMS

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Annotation

This article deals with a number of scientific considerations about further improving the speech skills of students in English classes.

Key words: English as a Foreign Language, teacher, school, education, speech, skills, class, conditions, knowledge

With the advent of modern technologies in teaching a foreign language, the development of writing skills becomes of great importance and becomes an object of research for many modern scientists. Over the past decades, the foreign language lesson has changed more than once, and with the advent of information and communication technologies, teachers and students have received completely new opportunities for their activities.

In this article, we will consider the stages of formation of writing skills in different periods of development of foreign language teaching methods. We will also consider the psychological and pedagogical features of writing, which must be taken into account when forming writing skills. The purpose of this article is to analyze the process of formation of writing skills, based on the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of a person, as well as to trace whether at all stages of learning, writing is an independent type of speech activity. Scientists identify six different stages in the development of foreign language teaching methods.

Each stage is characterized by its own characteristics in teaching various types of speech activity. The first stage of development occurred in 1917-1930. The main condition of this period was to keep the subject "Foreign language" in school education. Therefore, during this period, writing was not taught at school. The focus of the training was the text and the ability to understand it. The next period covers

the war and post-war years. During this period, they taught reading and text translation. At this stage, there was a refusal to teach oral speech. Written speech served as an auxiliary learning tool, i.e. it was used to take notes. In the 1960s, interest in the language increased, and with him, the principles of learning began to change, but writing was still only an auxiliary means of teaching other types of speech activity. The fourth stage of the development of the methodology of teaching foreign languages was characterized by the fact that the training was aimed at the development of speech activity, but writing was still given a secondary role. With the advent of the TSO (1980s), the fifth stage of the development of the teaching methodology begins. Independent work of schoolchildren plays a huge role here. Also at this stage, various areas of methodology were widely used, one of which was the communicative teaching method. Thus, speech activity in its main manifestations becomes the leading one: speaking, listening, reading, writing. This methodological concept received its psychological justification in the work of I.A. Zimnaya and in a number of works by other authors.

The next stage in the development of the methodology teaching foreign languages reflects its modern development. Modern methodology considers such qualities as communication, consistency, and functionality as the main properties of a foreign language. The basis of teaching a foreign language is communicative competence, the successful formation of which depends on the formation of all the skills of speech activity: reading, speaking, listening and writing. At this stage of the development of society, the social order is changing, which becomes fundamental at the next stage of the development of writing skills. With the advent of Web 2.0 technologies, a modern person should be able not only to speak and read in a foreign language, but also to express his thoughts in writing, because communication today has been partially transferred to a virtual educational environment, and his successful interaction with other people depends on how a person is able to express his thoughts in writing. Scientists are beginning to identify various skills of writing in a foreign language: for example, to write a personal letter, a greeting card, correctly arranging them from the point of view of etiquette, fill out a simple form (in a hotel, at when making an application), write the most elementary note asking you to come, call, and also make extracts of the necessary information from the text. E.N. Solovova identifies the following objectives of teaching writing: to teach students to write in a foreign language the same texts that an educated person can write in their native language: filling out questionnaires, writing various types of letters and answers to them, including both personal and official, writing an autobiography / resume, writing applications (including about employment,

enrollment, etc.), writing reviews, writing annotations, writing reports, writing essays / essays, writing greeting cards, writing notes.

N.D. Galskova puts forward the development of students' skills to express their thoughts in writing as the final requirements in the field of teaching writing. Students should be able to make extracts from the text within the most typical communication situations, compose and record a plan of the text they read or listened to, write a short greeting, express a wish, fill out a form in writing (specify first name, last name, gender, age, citizenship, address , etc.), write a personal letter in which ask the addressee about his life, affairs, tell the same about himself, express gratitude using the material of one or more topics learned in oral speech, using the formulas of speech etiquette adopted in the country of the language being studied. In the book "Methods of teaching foreign languages: traditions and modernity" edited by academician A.A. Mirolyubov, the authors list the following skills of writing in a foreign language for high school graduates at the basic level: write a personal and business letter and provide information about yourself in the accepted form (autobiography, resume / questionnaire, form); present the content of the read (listened to) foreign language text in theses, abstracts, reviews; briefly record the main content of the teacher's speech. the establishment.

These skills of writing in a foreign language are reflected in the Federal State Educational Standard of Basic General Education, which defines what a school graduate should learn in different types of speech activity in a foreign language at different levels of education. The Federal State standard imposes the following requirements on the student's writing skills at the basic level.

1. Be able to make extracts from the text.
2. Be able to write short greetings (happy birthday, happy other holiday), express wishes.
3. Be able to fill out the form (specify first name, last name, age, citizenship, address).
4. Be able to write a personal letter without relying on a sample (to ask the addressee about his life, affairs, to report the same about himself, express gratitude, request), using the material of topics learned in oral speech, using the formulas of speech etiquette adopted in the country of the language being studied. Nevertheless, in order for the student to learn how to successfully create written messages in a foreign language and communicate successfully, the teacher must remember that the writing process is a complex psychological and pedagogical process that has its own characteristics.

Therefore, when a student learns to write in a foreign language, he often has problems communicating his thoughts in the form of a written message. Students make various mistakes: when writing words, children skip letters, violate the order of words in a sentence, confuse the use of articles, make grammatical errors, which can be explained by the lack of properly formed initial skills.

Accordingly, there are a number of differences in the construction of written and oral speech. A person's oral speech is based on experiences. Written speech, on the contrary, is thoughtful and conscious. It can be concluded that the writing process includes there are many different components and affects different parts of the brain that are interconnected. Thus, having studied the research of scientists devoted to the psychological and pedagogical features of the origin of written speech, as well as the stages of formation and development of requirements for writing skills in a foreign language, we believe that At first, writing acted as an auxiliary activity of students, but gradually, complicating the exercises, writing turned into an independent skill that a student can use in real life to carry out written intercultural communication.

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